

CHEMICAL SCIENCES

APPLICATION OF DIBROMOBENZOATE Mn,Co,Cr IN LIQUID PHASE AEROBIC OXIDATION OF NAPHTHENE-PARAFFIN CONCENTRATE

Afandiyeva L.

*Doctor of Chemical Science of the
Institute of Petrochemical Processes*

Nasibova G.

*Candidate of Chemical Science of the
Institute of Petrochemical Processes*

Cherepnova Yu.

*Candidate of Chemical Science of the
Institute of Petrochemical Processes*

Chingiz F.

Researcher

Najafov T.

Master degree of the High Oil School

Abstract

The results of a study of the oxidation reaction of naphthene-paraffin concentrate obtained from a mixture of Azerbaijani petroleum in the presence of dibromobenzoate metals in the liquid phase are presented. It has been shown that the synthesized transition metal salts can be used as effective catalysts in the reactions of liquid-phase oxidation of naphthene-paraffin concentrate to produce synthetic petroleum acids.

Keywords: liquid-phase oxidation, catalyst, naphthene-paraffin concentrate, synthetic petroleum acids.

Introduction

The oxidation of hydrocarbons is a complex way of converting them into parallel and sequentially formed oxygen-containing products: hydroperoxides, alcohols, ketones, aldehydes, ethers, alcohols, etc. Numerous studies in this area show that hydrocarbons in the absence of a catalyst are more difficult to oxidize, because oxidation reactions are carried out at high temperatures and in the presence of catalysts. It is planned that the choice of the structure of the catalyst and the metal contained in the system will make it possible to find the most appropriate type of catalyst, allowing to accelerate the process of destruction of hydrocarbons into oxidation products. There are many works in the literature on the liquid-phase oxidation of petroleum fractions in the presence of metal salts of variable valence [1], bromine-containing carbon nanostructures [2], graphene [3], etc., characterized as positive process systems.

There is information in the literature [4] on the use of Ni, Pd and Pt on foils as an effective catalyst in the oxidation of alkanes (methane, ethane, propane, n-butane and isobutane) in the presence of atmospheric oxygen. In the work [5], aliphatic hydrocarbons were oxidized with atmospheric oxygen using an iron-containing catalyst ($[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_2(\text{OH})] \cdot [\text{Fe}(\text{Cl})_2\text{L}]$). This catalyst had a significant catalytic effect on the oxidation of n-decane, hexane, gasoline and diesel fuel.

It seemed interesting to us to carry out oxidation reactions of petroleum hydrocarbons in the presence of catalysts of a different nature and composition, i.e. containing metal and non-metal.

Experimental Part

For this purpose we synthesized catalysts based on bromobenzoic acid containing Mn, Co, Cr, the choice of which was characterized by the possibility of forming a complex ($\text{M}^{3+} \dots \text{Br}$), accelerating the limiting stage of the process - electron transfer from the substrate to the metal ion located in the highest valence state. To do this, calculated amounts of bromobenzoic acid were placed in the flask, a 20% aqueous solution of potassium hydroxide was added and the resulting mixture was stirred for 10-15 minutes. Then 10% aqueous solutions of metal salts were prepared: crystalline hydrate of manganese (II) sulfate $\text{MnSO}_4 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$, crystalline hydrate of chromium (III) nitrate $\text{Cr}(\text{NO}_3)_3 \cdot 9\text{H}_2\text{O}$, crystalline hydrate of cobalt (II) nitrate $\text{Co}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$. The resulting solutions in stoichiometric quantities were added to a solution of potassium bromobenzoate at a temperature of 60-80°C and stirred for 40 minutes. The resulting Mn, Co and Cr dibromobenzoates were dried and used in the oxidation of petroleum hydrocarbons.

Synthesized dibromobenzoates Mn, Co, Cr were used as a catalyst for the oxidation of naphthene-paraffin concentrates isolated from the diesel fraction of 190-350 °C mixture of Azerbaijani petroleum. The process was carried out using molecular oxygen at atmospheric pressure with a flow of 300 l/kg·h, at a temperature of 135-140 °C, varying the amount of catalyst with a reaction duration of 5 hours.

Results and Discussion

The results of catalytic oxidation of the naphthene-paraffin concentrates in the presence of dibromobenzoates Mn, Co, Cr are set into Tab.1,2,3

Table 1.

The results of oxidation reaction of naphthene-paraffin concentrates in the presence of dibromobenzoates Mn, Co, Cr catalyst (T= 135-140 °C, air supply rate 300 l/kg•h, reaction time 5h)

Catalyst, %	Oxidate		SPA+ OSPA	
	Acid number, mgKOH/g	Yield, %	T.Ə, mąKOH/q	Çıxım %
0,1	62	92,1	132,6	23,4
0,2	62	93,32	140	24
0,3	65	94,8	141,3	25,6
0,4	66,8	95	149,5	27,7
0,5	69,6	93,7	155	29,4
0,6	71,4	96	157,4	29,8
0,7	72,6	97	158,4	30,6
0,8	74	97	160	37,5
0,9	75	98	165	40,5
1,0	72,5	96	160,9	37,9

Table 2.

The results of oxidation reaction of naphthene-paraffin concentrates in the presence of dibromobenzoates Co, Cr catalyst (T= 135-140 °C, air supply rate 300 l/kg•h, reaction time 5h)

Catalyst, %	Oxidate		SPA+ OSPA	
	Acid number, mgKOH/g	Yield, %	T.Ə, mąKOH/q	Çıxım %
0,1	49	92,1	111,2	21,4
0,5	50,4	93,32	110	24
0,7	53	94,8	124,3	27,6
0,9	60	95	139,5	31,8
1,0	54,3	94	136,9	29

Table 3.

The results of oxidation reaction of naphthene-paraffin concentrates in the presence of dibromobenzoate Cr catalyst (T= 135-140 °C, air supply rate 300 l/kg•h, reaction time 5h)

Catalyst, %	Oxidate		SPA+ OSPA	
	Acid number, mgKOH/g	Yield, %	T.Ə, mąKOH/q	Çıxım %
0,1	44,8	91	111,2	18
0,5	52	93	110	18,6
0,7	56,5	95,2	124,3	20,6
0,9	62,5	98	139,5	21,9
1,0	58,9	96	136,9	19

Thus, as a result of the oxidation reaction of a mixture of Azerbaijani oils of the 190 - 350 °C fraction, the highest yield of petroleum acids was achieved in the presence of a catalyst Mn dibromobenzoate of the raw material equal to 40.5 wt. %, when the amount of catalyst used is 0.9%

The main reason for the high yield is believed to be the quality of the catalyst used. Namely, the presence in the system of metals with transitional valence that promote the formation of free radicals or atoms that allow the growth of hydrocarbon oxidation. When bromide ions are introduced into the reaction system, a

new route for the oxidation of hydrocarbons appears with the participation of bromine atoms formed in redox reactions: the metal, giving up 1 electron, ensures the transfer of an electron, which accelerates the formation of free radicals, and bromine, in turn, accelerates the process of electron transfer. The effect of the two resulting ions on the process of hydrocarbon oxidation has a positive effect on the yield of the final products [6].

References

1. Petrov S.M., Kayukova G.P., Lakhova A.Ī. [et al.] Low-temperature oxidation of heavy oil in a carbonate environment with cobalt (III) acetylacetonate // Chemistry and technology of fuels and oils. – 2017, №4. C.31-37
2. Zeynalov E.B., Friedrich J.F., Hidde G., Nasibova G.Q. [et al.] Brominated carbon nanotubes as effective catalyst for petroleum hydrocarbons aerobic oxidation // Oil Gas European Magazine. -2012. V.4. - p.45-48
3. Abbasov V.M., Afandiyeva L.M. Nasibova G.G., Aliyeva N.M., Ahmadbayova S.F., Shafizada S.M. Catalytic Properties of nanostructured graphene in liquid-phase oxidation of naphthene-paraffin hydrocarbons of petroleum mineral oils. Processes of Petrochemistry and Oil Refining, Baku, 2024, Vol.25, No.1, p.3-1
4. Mansour Aryafar, Francisco Zaera. Kinetic study of the catalytic oxidation of alkanes over nickel, palladium, and platinum foils // Catalysis Letters, 1997, v. 48, p.173-183
5. Melvin K. C. Catalytic air oxidation of ambient temperature hydrocarbons // Molecular Catalysis A: Chemical 200, 2003, p.191-203
6. Potechin V. M., Potechin V. V. B. Osnovy teorii khimicheskikh protsessov organicheskikh veshchestv i neftepererabotki (Principles of the Theory of Chemical Processes in the Technology of Organic Compounds and Oil Refining), St. Petersburg: Khimizdat, 2005, p. 344